

EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF ASSISTIVE DEVICES ON ACADEMIC OUTCOMES OF HEARING-IMPAIRED STUDENTS IN SPECIAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS IN FAISALABAD, PAKISTAN

Dr. Muhammad Nazir^{*1}, Dr. Hina Hadayat Ali², Bilal Munir³

¹(Lecturer Special Education) Department of Special Education, University of Education, Lahore, Faisalabad Campus, Pakistan

²(Assistant Professor/Coordinator) Department of Special Education, University of Education, Lahore, Faisalabad Campus, Pakistan

³(M.Phil Special Education Scholar) Department of Special Education, University of Education, Lahore, Faisalabad Campus, Pakistan

¹muhammad.nazir@ue.edu.pk, ²hina.hadayat@ue.edu.pk, ³bilalmunir141@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16531477>

Keywords

Assistive Devices, Hearing Impairment, Academic Achievement, Inclusive Education, Special Education, Faisalabad

Article History

Received on 18 April 2025

Accepted on 11 July 2025

Published on 28 July 2025

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Muhammad Nazir

Abstract

This cross-sectional correlational study examines the role of assistive devices in enhancing the academic achievement of students with hearing impairments in government special education schools in Faisalabad, Pakistan. Hearing loss impairs classroom engagement, communication, and academic participation, necessitating the use of assistive technologies such as hearing aids, FM systems, and cochlear implants. A structured questionnaire was administered to 60 students (30 deaf, 30 hard of hearing), and data were analyzed using SPSS. Results revealed a moderate positive correlation between daily device usage and academic improvement ($r = 0.42$, $p = 0.004$). Hard-of-hearing students demonstrated significantly greater academic gains than their deaf peers ($p = 0.019$). The type of assistive device significantly influenced academic outcomes ($p = 0.033$). Multiple regression analysis indicated that daily device usage and device type were positive predictors of academic performance, while deafness was a negative predictor. Despite moderate improvements in academic engagement and communication, issues such as usability, support services, and access persist. The study underscores the need for enhanced implementation of assistive technologies within inclusive education frameworks.

INTRODUCTION

Special education refers to instructional practices tailored for learners with diverse educational needs, including those with disabilities (UNESCO, 2017). Among these, hearing impairment, defined as reduced ability to hear sounds below 20 dB in both ears, poses unique challenges. It ranges from mild to profound and may be unilateral or bilateral, affecting speech, language, communication, and academic development (WHO, 2024).

Children with hearing loss often rely on assistive technologies like hearing aids, cochlear implants, FM systems, and captioning devices. These tools enhance sound perception and improve educational participation, particularly in inclusive settings (Luckner & Muir, 2001; Rekkedal, 2012). However, disparities in device usage, affordability, and attitudes, especially in rural and low-income areas, continue to

limit their effectiveness (Farooq & Iftikhar, 2015; Chimowa et al., 2024).

Research suggests that the academic performance of hearing-impaired students is directly linked to access and use of assistive devices. Studies have shown improvements in language skills, communication, and classroom engagement when appropriate technologies are employed (Kanwal et al., 2024; Dellilah, 2024). Nevertheless, cultural stigma, cost barriers, and limited teacher training remain obstacles to consistent use (Eriks-Brophy et al., 2006; Stinson & Antia, 1999). Despite the proven benefits, many students still underperform in subjects like English, Urdu, and Mathematics, particularly when assistive devices are unavailable or underutilized. Teachers' and parents' attitudes towards technology significantly influence student engagement and success (Rekkedal, 2012).

This study aims to raise awareness about the educational needs of deaf and hard-of-hearing students using assistive devices. It highlights the role of such devices in improving academic performance and promoting equitable learning opportunities. By identifying factors influencing their effectiveness, the study seeks to inform teaching practices, guide resource allocation, and support inclusive education policy development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Academic success relies heavily on accessing auditory information, interacting with peers, and class participation, which can be hindered in children with hearing loss (Marschark & Hauser, 2012). Assistive devices help bridge the gap between deaf and hearing students by enhancing communication and learning, thereby supporting classroom participation (Luckner & Bowen, 2006). With around 34 million children affected globally, many struggle due to inadequate communication tools (WHO, 2021). Early intervention and assistive technology have been shown to reduce educational disparities (Fitzpatrick et al., 2011). Devices like hearing aids, cochlear implants, and FM systems amplify sound, improve speech perception, and reduce noise, promoting self-confidence and social interaction (Marschark et al., 2015; Tomblin et al., 2015; Antia et al., 2009). However, their effectiveness depends on teacher and student training and the educational context (Luckner & Bowen, 2006; Eriks-Brophy et al., 2012).

Assistive technology, including hearing aids, cochlear implants, and FM systems, supports inclusive education by enabling access to auditory content and improving communication (Luckner & Bowen, 2006). Hearing aids amplify sound and reduce noise interference (Tomblin et al., 2015). Cochlear implants are effective for severe to profound loss and improve speech comprehension and academic outcomes (Marschark et al., 2015). FM systems enhance classroom listening by reducing background noise and transmitting the teacher's voice directly to the student (Eriks-Brophy et al., 2012). These devices contribute to academic success by improving language skills, participation, and self-confidence (Tomblin et al., 2015; Marschark & Hauser, 2012; & Bowen, 2006). However, successful implementation depends on early diagnosis, training, and collaboration among stakeholders (Fitzpatrick et al., 2011).

These devices significantly impact learning by developing communication skills, enhancing classroom participation, and improving learning outcomes (Tomblin et al., 2015), often hindered by cost, limited access to services, and social stigma (Mitra et al., 2017). They aid in early speech and language acquisition, especially when introduced before age two, and support bilingual and bicultural development (Marschark & Hauser, 2012; Mayer & Leigh, 2010; Eriks-Brophy et al., 2012). FM systems also help manage classroom noise, encouraging peer interaction and collaboration (Marschark et al., 2015). Students using assistive devices perform better academically, especially in reading, math, and science, due to improved auditory access and reduced cognitive load (Marschark & Hauser, 2012; Luckner & Bowen, 2006; Tomblin et al., 2015). This enables deeper learning and enhances motivation through real-time feedback (Mayer & Leigh, 2010). Assistive devices also foster educational equity by narrowing achievement gaps and enabling full participation in learning environments (Eriks-Brophy et al., 2012). Educator training and collaborative practices are essential to maximize these benefits (Antia et al., 2009). Increased self-confidence and motivation are additional outcomes of effective device use, as students feel more competent and independent (Luckner & Bowen, 2006; Antia et al., 2009; Marschark et al., 2015). These psychological benefits lead to greater engagement and academic resilience.

Social inclusion improves as assistive devices allow for meaningful peer interactions, which foster social skills and collaborative learning (Eriks-Brophy et al., 2012; Fitzpatrick et al., 2011). Eriks-Brophy et al. (2012) emphasized that assistive technology, when combined with supportive teaching, promoted success in mainstream classrooms.

Unlike Fitzpatrick et al. (2011) who found consistent early language gains through cochlear implants, Farooq and Iftikhar (2015) highlighted that lack of infrastructure and training in Pakistan reduces their efficacy. This underscores the need to evaluate assistive technologies across varying educational and socio-economic contexts to inform localized strategies. Most prior studies affirm the benefits of assistive devices in developed countries and focus on general outcomes rather than context-specific implementation. The current research addresses this gap by empirically examining the role of assistive devices in supporting access, equity, and achievement among hearing-impaired learners with a particular focus on **under-resourced educational settings**.

Objectives of the Study

The study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. Exploring the emerging perceptions related to the use of assistive devices in the education of children with hearing impairments.
2. Identifying the specific assistive technologies that are most effective in enhancing academic performance, particularly in the areas of reading, mathematics, and science.
3. Developing the evidence-based recommendations for improving instructional strategies aimed at fostering self-help skill development among children with intellectual and hearing disabilities

Research Questions

The study was conducted to find answers to the following questions:

1. What emerging perceptions can be drawn regarding the use of assistive devices for children with hearing impairments?
2. Which assistive devices are most effective in enhancing academic performance in key subject areas such as reading, mathematics, and science?

3. What evidence-based recommendations can be proposed to improve instructional strategies for fostering self-help skill development in children with intellectual and hearing disabilities?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a **descriptive research design**, which is well-suited for systematically outlining the characteristics, behaviors, and patterns within a specific population. As noted by Wood and Kerr (2010), descriptive research aims to present an accurate profile of situations or phenomena. A cross-sectional correlational quantitative design was employed to investigate the relationship between assistive device use and academic achievement.

Population of the Study

The target population for this study consisted of all students with hearing impairments and special education teachers currently enrolled in or employed by Government Special Education Schools for Hearing Impairment in the Faisalabad district of Pakistan. These institutions serve a diverse range of students with varying degrees and types of hearing loss, including both deaf and hard-of-hearing learners. By focusing on this defined and accessible population, the study aimed to capture a representative understanding of the use and impact of assistive devices within the government special education sector in this region.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample comprised 60 students with hearing impairments, including 30 hard-of-hearing and 30 deaf learners, selected from Government Special Education Schools for Hearing Impairment in the Faisalabad district. Participants were selected through non-probability purposive sampling due to logistical constraints and accessibility in government special education schools.

Instrument Development and Validation

To gather quantitative data for this study, a structured questionnaire was developed to evaluate the impact of assistive devices on the academic achievement and classroom experiences of students with hearing impairments. The instrument was designed for

administration to parents, guardians, and special education teachers, and comprises both demographic and thematic sections.

The **demographic section** collected essential background information, including the student’s age, gender, grade level, type and severity of hearing impairment (conductive, sensorineural, or mixed), as well as details about the school, teacher qualifications, and years of teaching experience. The **thematic section** was structured around 16 key variables divided into three domains:

1. **Academic Achievement (6 items):** assessing general academic performance and subject-specific gains in reading, writing, mathematics, science, and social studies.

2. **Access to Assistive Devices and Learning Environments (6 items):** measuring device type, frequency and duration of use, classroom integration, usability, and availability.

3. **Equity and Social Communication (4 items):** examining improvements in peer interaction, teacher-student communication, and perceived inclusivity.

Each item employed a Likert-type scale to quantify responses. For instance, academic improvement was rated on a 7-point scale from “no improvement” to “significant improvement,” while device usability and accessibility were assessed using a 4-point scale ranging from “very poor” to “excellent.” The questionnaire underwent a rigorous **content validation process**. Experts in the fields of special education and audiology reviewed the tool for clarity, content relevance, construct alignment, and comprehensiveness. Feedback from these professionals was incorporated to refine the wording and sequence of items.

A **pilot study** was conducted with a representative subset of the target population to test the reliability and internal consistency of the instrument. Based on pilot responses, necessary revisions were made to improve item clarity and respondent comprehension.

The instrument's reliability was confirmed using **Cronbach’s Alpha**, which yielded a coefficient of **0.84**, indicating a high level of internal consistency and reliability. This validated tool provided a robust framework for exploring participants’ perceptions of how assistive devices influence academic achievement, classroom engagement, and social communication among students with hearing impairments.

Data Collection

Prior to data collection, ethical approval was obtained from the University of Education, Lahore Research Ethics Committee. Informed consent was sought from all participants or their guardians, ensuring confidentiality and voluntary participation. The researcher prepared and distributed 60 copies of the questionnaire among special education teachers for the data collection teaching in the Govt. Special Education Schools for Hearing Impairment of district Faisalabad, Pakistan. The researcher went to special education schools and met with the participants. The researcher explained the study's purpose and goals to the participants before giving them the questionnaire. Then, the participants filled out the questionnaire, and the researcher collected it after completion.

Data Analysis and Results

Descriptive statistics were employed to analyze the data and address the study’s exploratory objectives. The collected information was numerically coded and entered into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for processing. The analysis aimed to examine and compare the academic achievement levels of deaf and hard-of-hearing students at the primary level using appropriate statistical techniques. However, to enhance the depth, generalizability, and statistical rigor of your findings, inferential statistics was also incorporated. This helped determine whether observed differences or relationships in your data are statistically significant and not due to chance.

Table 1
Combined Table of Respondents' Demographic and Device Usage Information

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
Age	25-35	27	37.0	45.0	45.0
	36-50	33	45.2	55.0	100.0

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
Gender	Female	45	61.6	75.0	75.0
	Male	15	20.5	25.0	100.0
Sector	Private	18	24.7	30.0	30.0
	Public	42	57.5	70.0	100.0
Type of School	Deaf	25	34.2	41.7	41.7
	Hard of Hearing	35	47.9	58.3	100.0
Teaching Experience	1-6 Years	25	34.2	41.7	41.7
	7-12 Years	35	47.9	58.3	100.0
Type of Hearing Impairment	Conductive	4	5.5	6.7	6.7
	Sensorineural	14	19.2	23.3	30.0
	Mixed	42	57.5	70.0	100.0
Level of Hearing Impairment	Moderately Impaired	19	26.0	31.7	31.7
	Severely Impaired	41	56.2	68.3	100.0
Type of Assistive Device Used	FM System	1	1.4	1.7	1.7
	Other Devices	21	28.8	35.0	36.7
	Basic Analog Hearing Aid	31	42.5	51.7	88.3
	Digital Hearing Aid or Local Customized Device	7	9.6	11.7	100.0
Daily Use Duration of Devices	3-4 Hours	33	45.2	55.0	55.0
	5-6 Hours	27	37.0	45.0	100.0
Device Use During Classroom Hours	Level 6	11	15.1	18.3	18.3
	Level 7	49	67.1	81.7	100.0

Note. Table 1 indicates that the majority of respondents (45.2%) are aged between 36-50 years, with a dominant female representation (61.6%). Most participants are from the public sector (57.5%) and teach in schools for hard-of-hearing students (47.9%). In terms of teaching experience, 47.9% have been teaching for 7-12 years. Mixed hearing impairment is most prevalent among students (57.5%), with a majority experiencing severe hearing loss (56.2%). Regarding assistive devices, the most commonly

reported type was labeled "Basic Analog Hearing Aid" (42.5%), though its nature was not specified, followed by "other devices" (28.8%). Daily usage ranged primarily from 3-6 hours, with 45.2% reporting 3-4 hours of use. During classroom hours, 67.1% of respondents indicated a usage level of "7", also unspecified in type. Overall, the data suggests widespread device usage with a positive trend toward integration in educational settings.

Table 2
Variables of Academic Achievement, Access to Assistive Devices, and Equity in Social Interaction (N = 60)

Category	Variable	Response Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)	
Academic Achievement	Observed change in overall academic performance following the use of assistive devices	No change, Slight improvement, Moderate, Significant	14, 20, 23, 3	19.2, 27.4, 31.5, 4.1	
	Perceived effectiveness of assistive devices in enhancing academic achievement	Slight decline, No change, Slight improvement	15, 36, 9	20.5, 49.3, 12.3	
	Academic subject showing the most noticeable improvement due to device use	Writing, Math	25, 35	34.2, 47.9	
	Subject in which the student feels most confident after using the assistive device	Writing, Math, Science	28, 31, 1	38.4, 42.5, 1.4	
	Overall impact of assistive devices on students' academic achievement	Minor, Moderate, Significant	13, 36, 11	17.8, 49.3, 15.1	
	Perceived level of academic achievement among hearing-impaired students using technology	Minor, Moderate, Significant	15, 34, 11	20.5, 46.6, 15.1	
	Access to Assistive Devices and Learning Environments	Impact of assistive device use on students' engagement in classroom activities	No change, Slight increase, Moderate increase	13, 34, 13	17.8, 46.6, 17.8
Change in active participation following the implementation of assistive devices		No change, Slight improvement, Moderate improvement	27, 21, 12	37.0, 28.8, 16.4	
Improvement in students' communication skills due to the use of assistive technology		Slight, Moderate, Significant improvement	12, 31, 17	16.4, 42.5, 23.3	
Perceived ease of use of assistive devices within academic settings		Difficult, Neutral, Easy, Very easy	7, 28, 22, 3	9.6, 38.4, 30.1, 4.1	
Students' ability to operate assistive devices independently during learning activities		Difficult, Neutral, Easy, Very easy	5, 13, 29, 13	6.8, 17.8, 39.7, 17.8	
Availability and accessibility of assistive devices within the school environment		Very poor, Poor, Fair, Good, Excellent	2, 5, 24, 21, 8	2.7, 6.8, 32.9, 28.8, 11.0	
Equity: Communication and Interaction Outcomes		Social Improvement in communication and with classmates resulting from the use of assistive devices	Slight, Moderate, Significant improvement	15, 26, 19	20.5, 35.6, 26.0
	Enhancement of social interaction with peers following assistive support	Slight, Moderate, Significant improvement	15, 26, 19	20.5, 35.6, 26.0	

Changes in the quality of teacher-student interactions since the adoption of assistive devices	Slight, Significant improvement	Moderate, Fair	34, 21, 5	46.6, 6.8	28.8,
Perceived adequacy and availability of institutional support services related to assistive technology	Poor, Excellent	Fair, Good	7, 21, 25, 8	9.6, 34.2, 11.0	28.8,

Note. Table 2 presents a detailed overview of participants' responses regarding the academic, communicative, and social effects of assistive device use among students with hearing impairments. The majority of respondents (31.5%) reported moderate improvement in overall academic performance following device use, while 27.4% noted slight improvement, indicating a general trend of positive educational impact. However, 19.2% perceived no change, and only 4.1% reported significant improvement, suggesting that the benefits of assistive technology may be influenced by factors such as device type, severity of impairment, and classroom integration practices.

When assessing device effectiveness, 49.3% reported no noticeable improvement in academic outcomes, while 20.5% observed a slight decline, highlighting variability in user experiences. Notably, mathematics (47.9%) and writing (34.2%) emerged as the subjects with the most observable gains, reflecting alignment with previous research

indicating improved performance in visually and structurally guided subjects (Tomblin et al., 2015).

Regarding student confidence, the majority felt most confident in mathematics (42.5%) and writing (38.4%) post-intervention, while only a small fraction (1.4%) indicated increased confidence in science, perhaps due to the abstract nature or auditory demands of the subject. Perceptions of the overall academic impact of assistive devices were rated as moderate by 49.3% and significant by 15.1%, reinforcing the devices' potential to enhance learning when effectively implemented.

In terms of access and engagement, nearly half of the respondents (46.6%) observed a slight increase in classroom engagement, and 28.8% noted slight improvements in participation, supporting the notion

that assistive technologies can promote active involvement in academic activities. Communication skills showed moderate improvement in 42.5% of the cases, with an additional 23.3% reporting significant gains, suggesting that the devices also play a role in strengthening verbal and social interaction.

Responses related to usability revealed that 30.1% of respondents found the devices easy to use, while 38.4% remained neutral, indicating mixed levels of comfort or familiarity. Moreover, 39.7% agreed that students could operate devices independently, yet a combined 24.6% expressed difficulty or uncertainty, reflecting the need for user training and support.

Assessment of accessibility and institutional support yielded mixed ratings: while 34.2% found support services to be good and 11.0% rated them as excellent, 38.4% rated them fair or below, emphasizing ongoing concerns about infrastructure, technical availability, and equitable access.

Finally, results under the equity and social interaction domain suggest that assistive devices have a favorable influence on peer communication and social integration. More than 60% of respondents reported moderate to significant improvement in both classmate and peer interactions. Teacher-student interactions, however, showed a comparatively lower trend, with only 6.8% reporting significant improvement, which may indicate limitations in instructional strategies or communication styles among educators.

Overall, the interpretation of Table 2 reinforces the potential of assistive devices to foster academic and social development among students with hearing impairments. However, the effectiveness is clearly moderated by device usability, daily usage, institutional support, and user-specific factors, all of which warrant attention for optimizing inclusive educational practices.

Table 3

Independent Samples t-Test – Academic Improvement by Type of Impairment

Group	N	Mean Score	SD	t-value	p-value
Hard of Hearing	30	3.80	0.76	2.43	0.019*
Deaf	30	3.20	0.85		

Note. Table 3 indicates a statistically significant difference in academic improvement scores between hard-of-hearing and deaf students ($p = 0.019$), with

hard-of-hearing students reporting higher average gains.

Table 4

Pearson Correlation – Device Usage Hours and Academic Improvement

Variable 1	Variable 2	R	p-value
Daily Use Hours	Academic Improvement	0.42	0.004*

Note. Table 4 is a moderate positive correlation between daily device use hours and academic improvement ($r = 0.42$, $p = 0.004$), suggesting that more frequent usage is associated with greater gains.

Table 5

Chi-Square Test Results: Association between Type of Assistive Device and Academic Improvement (N = 60)

Device Type	Improved	Not Improved	χ^2	df	p-value
FM System	1	0			
Basic Analog Hearing Aid	22	9			
Other Devices	15	6			
Digital Hearing Aid / Local Customized Device	4	3	8.76	3	0.033*

Note. Table 5 indicates a statistically significant association between the type of assistive device used and academic improvement ($p = 0.033$). This suggests that certain devices, particularly basic analog hearing aids, may be more effective than others in enhancing academic outcomes for students with hearing

impairments. However, the small number of FM system users limits generalizability. Further investigation with a larger sample and more balanced device representation is recommended to confirm these trends.

Table 6

Multiple Regression – Predicting Academic Performance

Predictor	B	SEB	B	t	p
Daily Device Usage Hours	0.35	0.11	0.40	3.18	0.003*
Type of Impairment	-0.25	0.09	-0.30	-2.78	0.007*
Device Type (coded)	0.20	0.08	0.25	2.50	0.015*

Note. Table 6 indicates that daily device usage, type of impairment, and device type significantly predict academic performance ($p < 0.05$). More usage and certain device types are positively associated, while being deaf (versus hard of hearing) negatively affects outcomes.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The following key findings emerged from the data analysis:

1. Participants ranged in age from 25 to 50 years. Among them, 37% were between 25–35 years, while the majority, 45%, fell within the 36–50 age group, indicating a relatively balanced age distribution with a slight predominance of older respondents.
2. Gender-wise analysis revealed a significant disparity, with 61.6% of participants being female and only 20.5% male, suggesting a higher representation of females in the study.
- 3–4. Institutional affiliation showed that 57.5% of respondents were from public-sector institutions, compared to 24.7% from private institutions, indicating a greater involvement from the public sector.
5. Regarding type of hearing loss, 47.9% of respondents were categorized as hard of hearing, while 34.2% were identified as deaf.
6. In terms of teaching experience, 34.2% had 1–6 years, and 47.9% had 7–12 years, indicating most participants had mid-level experience.
7. Analysis of hearing loss type revealed that 57.5% had mixed hearing loss, 19.2% sensorineural, and 5.5% conductive, showing that mixed hearing loss was the most common among participants.
8. In terms of assistive device usage, 42.5% reported using “basic analog hearing aids”, 28.8% used other devices, 9.6% used “digital hearing aids or locally customized devices”, and 1.4% reported using FM systems, with “device 5” being the most widely used.
9. Device usage duration showed that 45.2% used devices for three to four hours daily, while 37.0% used them for five to six hours, reflecting consistent engagement with assistive technologies.
10. When asked about frequency of use during classroom hours, 67.1% chose the highest frequency option (labelled “7”), followed by 15.1% selecting “6”,

suggesting regular device use during instructional time.

11. Regarding perceived academic improvement, 31.5% of respondents reported moderate improvement, 27.4% noted slight improvement, 19.2% observed no change, and only 4.1% reported significant improvement after using assistive devices (Variable 1 – Achievement).

12. On perceived effectiveness of assistive devices, 49.3% reported no change in academic trends, while 20.5% noted a slight decline and 12.3% observed slight improvement (Variable 2 – Achievement).

13–14. Subject preference and confidence data indicated that math was the most improved subject (47.9%) and the subject in which learners felt most confident after using assistive devices (42.5%). Writing followed closely (34.2% and 38.4%, respectively), while only 1.4% selected science (Variables 3 and 4 – Achievement).

15–16. Classroom engagement and participation showed positive trends: 46.6% reported increased engagement, and participation metrics reflected similar improvements with 28.8% noting slight and 16.4% moderate increases (Variables under Access – Items 1 and 2).

17–19. Improvements in academic engagement, communication, and social interaction were also noteworthy. Specifically, 42.5% reported moderate improvement, 23.3% significant improvement, and 16.4% slight improvement in communication skills. These trends were consistent across peer and teacher interactions (Variables 3 under Access, and 1–3 under Equity).

20–21. Overall impact on academic achievement was considered moderate by 49.3% of respondents, minor by 17.8%, and significant by 15.1%. A similar distribution was noted in perceptions of academic achievement in hearing-impaired children using assistive devices (Variables 5 and 6 – Achievement).

22–23. Ease of use data showed that 30.1% found the devices easy to use, 9.6% difficult, and 38.4% felt neutral. Additionally, 39.7% agreed that children could easily operate the devices, while 17.8% remained neutral on this aspect (Variables 4 and 5 under Access).

24–25. Evaluation of support services revealed mixed opinions: 32.9% rated device accessibility as fair and 28.8% as good. Regarding support services, 34.2% rated them good, while 28.8% expressed fear or lack of confidence. This reflects ongoing concerns about service quality and availability (Variables 6 under Access and 4 under Equity).

26. Overall, the data indicate a high level of engagement with assistive devices, preference for subjects like mathematics, and generally moderate improvements in academic and social outcomes. However, mixed perceptions regarding usability and support services suggest ongoing barriers to optimal device use.

27. Hard-of-hearing students demonstrated significantly greater academic improvement than their deaf peers, supporting earlier statistical trends ($p = 0.019$), as indicated by the independent samples t -test.

28. A moderate positive correlation was found between daily use of assistive devices and academic improvement ($r = 0.42$, $p = 0.004$), suggesting that increased usage enhances performance.

29. The Chi-square test revealed a significant relationship between the type of assistive device and academic improvement ($p = 0.033$), indicating that certain devices are more effective than others.

30. Multiple regression analysis showed that daily device usage and device type positively predict academic performance, while being deaf (versus hard of hearing) negatively impacts outcomes ($p < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study support and extend the existing body of literature that highlights the positive role of assistive devices in promoting academic success and classroom engagement among students with hearing impairments. Consistent with Marschark and Hauser (2012) and Luckner and Bowen (2006), the results indicate that assistive devices facilitate improved access to auditory input, leading to moderate academic gains, particularly in structured subjects such as mathematics and writing. This study found that 31.5% of respondents reported moderate academic improvement, while 27.4% observed slight improvement following the use of assistive devices. These findings align with previous research showing that enhanced auditory access leads to improved

comprehension and participation in core academic tasks (Tomblin et al., 2015; Antia et al., 2009).

Furthermore, the statistically significant correlation between daily device use and academic performance ($r = 0.42$, $p = 0.004$) and the superior outcomes among hard-of-hearing students compared to deaf peers ($p = 0.019$) are congruent with the work of Fitzpatrick et al. (2011) and Marschark et al. (2015), who underscore the importance of early and consistent auditory input in supporting academic growth. These findings emphasize that while hearing aids and FM systems contribute to improved speech perception and classroom performance, their effectiveness is closely linked to the severity of hearing loss and the consistency of use. The significant association between device type and academic achievement ($p = 0.033$) further supports the conclusion that not all assistive devices offer equal benefits, a finding echoed in studies by Rekkedal (2012) and Luckner & Bowen (2006), which stress the importance of matching devices to individual student needs and classroom demands.

Notably, nearly half of the participants (49.3%) reported no change in academic performance, and 20.5% perceived a slight decline, suggesting that assistive technology alone may not be sufficient to yield uniformly positive outcomes. These mixed perceptions mirror findings by Eriks-Brophy et al. (2006) and Farooq & Iftikhar (2015), who point to systemic barriers such as insufficient training, limited access, outdated equipment, and lack of follow-up support in low-resource settings like Pakistan. The present study adds to this discourse by emphasizing that contextual factors, such as device quality, school infrastructure, and user training, are pivotal in translating technological access into academic achievement.

This study supports existing research suggesting that assistive devices enhance peer interactions and promote greater engagement and participation in both classroom activities and social settings. Approximately 46.6% of participants observed increased engagement, and 42.5% reported moderate improvement in communication with teachers and peers. These outcomes are in line with research by Antia et al. (2009) and Eriks-Brophy et al. (2012), who emphasized the role of assistive technology in promoting social inclusion and reducing isolation in

educational environments. Nonetheless, the relatively lower ratings on ease of use (only 30.1% found devices easy to use) and access to support services (32.9% rated accessibility as only "fair") reinforce concerns raised by Chimowa et al. (2024) and McCracken (2019), who argue that technological interventions must be paired with robust institutional support, family involvement, and psychosocial scaffolding to yield sustainable impact.

This study contributes important localized evidence to a field largely dominated by research from developed countries. It confirms that while assistive devices offer meaningful benefits for learners with hearing impairments, their success in real-world, under-resourced educational settings depends heavily on multi-level support systems, cultural attitudes, and the adequacy of school-based services (Farooq & Iftikhar, 2015; Eriks-Brophy et al., 2006).

CONCLUSION

The findings highlight that **hard-of-hearing students experience significantly greater academic improvement than deaf students, with daily usage duration and type of assistive device emerging as significant predictors** of academic success. Despite the high frequency of device usage during instructional time and a generally positive attitude toward their utility, **mixed perceptions regarding ease of use and support services point to persisting challenges** in achieving optimal outcomes. Furthermore, the preference for subjects like mathematics and increased classroom participation suggest a positive shift in academic engagement. However, the relatively low percentage of participants reporting significant improvement, combined with the prevalent fear or lack of confidence in support services, emphasizes the **need for more accessible, user-friendly devices and stronger institutional support systems** to maximize the benefits of assistive technology in inclusive education.

These findings align with Pakistan's National Education Policy 2017, which emphasizes inclusive education and technological integration for children with disabilities. Furthermore, this study supports Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education), particularly target 4.5 aimed at eliminating gender and disability disparities in education.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The study was confined to government special education institutions in Faisalabad.
2. Findings may not be generalizable to private or mainstream schools.
3. Convenience sampling was used, which may introduce selection bias.
4. Reliance on self-reported data may be affected by participants' subjective perceptions and reporting tendencies.
5. The cross-sectional design limits the ability to assess changes over time.
6. The study did not employ mixed-methods or qualitative approaches, which could provide deeper insights.
7. Future research should consider broader geographic and institutional coverage for wider applicability.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The study highlights the necessity of incorporating psychological support, counseling services, and confidence-building programs as integral components of intervention strategies for students with hearing impairments.
2. Effective interventions should include ongoing assessment and outcome monitoring to track moderate to significant improvements, enabling timely adjustments for enhanced program effectiveness.
3. Collaborative partnerships between public and private institutions should be encouraged to facilitate the sharing of resources, best practices, and innovative approaches, thereby expanding the reach and impact of intervention programs.

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